

ROLE OF CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AS A SECONDARY MODE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

All Round Development is the theme of the modern Education which emphasizes that when the child comes to the school, he comes to gain intellectual, Physical, Social, Spiritual and vocational smartness as such he must be educated and nourished in all of them. According to modern concept of education the three traditional 3R's should be replaced by 7R's i.e., Reading; Writing, Arithmetic, Rights, Responsibilities, Recreation and Relationship, this can be achieved only Providing a well-organized and supervised Program of Co-Curricular activities along with curricular programme. The objective of this study was to assess the status of implementation of Co-Curricular activities and suggest the possible solutions for the problem that encountered during implementation. This article may give insight idea on how much Co-Curricular activity can be implemented. It may also create an awareness of Co-Curricular activities that shows the strength and weakness of Co-Curricular program that has been implemented.

Key words: - *Co-Curricular activities, Schools, Teachers etc.*

Introduction

All Round Development is the theme of the modern Education which emphasizes that when the child comes to the school, he comes to gain intellectual Physical, Social, Spiritual and vocational smartness as such he must be educated and nourished in all of them. Holistic Development is basically the development of everyone's intellectual, emotional, social, physical, artistic, creative, religious values and feelings. It is pretty much just the development of the entire brain's thoughts and feelings. The all-round development or holistic development of an individual is only possible through balanced development of scholastic or academic as well as non-scholastic or non-academic aspects in the formal,

informal and non-formal educational setting in the society. Particularly, in the modern era where individual have to pass through phases of undue anxiety and over-stress, one finds that sometimes it leads to various types of depression and even loss of life. In such cases individual's involvement in the Co-Curricular activities become more significance Co-Curricular use these activities stop various types of anxieties and stress to come near the individual. Today, the burdens of "stunts in education" i.e. marks, grades, divisions etc. are also becoming fatal for growth and life of individuals across all societies in the world. The Co-Curricular activities help the student to overcome the stress of stunts and allow the holistic development of individual. The modern education system recognizes that child come to educational institution for all round and harmonious development.

Meaning of Co-Curricular Activities

Co-Curricular activities are the components of non-academic curriculum that helps to develop various facets of the personality development of the child and students. For all round development of the child, there is a need of emotional, physical, spiritual and moral development that is complemented and supplemented by Co-Curricular Activities. The meaning of Co-Curricular activities revolves around its different feature and characteristics. For the overall development of a child, curriculum is not only the single criteria. The holistic growth as well as to develop the various facets of personality development of children; classroom teaching should be supplemented with Co-Curricular activities. These out of class activities affect all domains of life such as cognitive (intellectual), emotional, social, moral, cultural and aesthetic. Co-Curricular activities meaning are more focused upon cognitive aspects thereby help in intellectual development. Competitiveness, excellence, quality achievements, creativeness and enthusiasm are few of the ethics of Co-Curricular activities. Non-academic activity in the form of Co-Curricular one provides support to students to venture into professional fields like fashion, music, painting, art, acting, photography, printing and many more.

Definitions of Co-Curricular Activities

The Co-Curricular activities definitions by leading modern educational thinkers and others are: The International Dictionary of Education (1977) "Activities sponsored or recognized by a school or college which are not part of the academic curriculum but are acknowledged to be an essential part of the life of an educational institution.

Aggarwal (2000) "Co-Curricular activities were mainly organized after school hours and so were the Co-Curricular but they are not an integral part of the activities of the school as its curricular work".

Bhatia (1996) “Co-Curricular activities may be defined as the activities undertaken to strengthen the classroom learning as well as other activities both inside and outside the classroom to develop the personality of the child”.

Development of Co-Curricular Activities

In Indian system of education Co-Curricular activities have always been given a high place of Importance. The ancient Indian hardly made any distinction between the learning activities which were to train their intellect from those which were to build them Physically, Morally and Emotionally.

In Vedic system of education ample opportunities were provided to the pupil for the development of his personality. In post Vedic system of education industrial and vocational training was essentially a practical and useful education. In the Brahminical system of education close contact between pupil outside the class helped a lot in the development of character and individuality of human being.

In the seventh century according to the account given by I – Tsing there were such physical and artistic activities popular among the students of Nalanda University as wrestling chariot, racing, mimicking and dancing.

Under the Islamic system of education, the practical activities were emphasized. The Swordsmanship, Riding, wrestling etc. were the activities which were emphasized in the training of the princes and the sons of the nobles.

Under the British system of education Co-Curricular activities were not considered very essential in a school instructional programme. Skill same provision of activities was made in each and every school. The school with experienced headmasters were giving them much more importance than the other for all round development of the child.

According to modern concept of education the three traditional 3R's should be replaced by 7R's i.e., Reading; Writing, Arithmetic, Rights, Responsibilities, Recreation and Relationship, this can be achieved only Providing a well-organized and supervised Program of Co-Curricular activities along with curricular programme.

According to secondary Education Commission (1952-53) in respect of the Co-Curricular activities “The School is not merely a place of formal learning whose main concern is to communicate a certain prescribed quantum of knowledge but rather as a living and organic community which is primarily interested in training its pupils in what we have called the gracious “ art of living” knowledge and learning are undoubtedly of value but they must be acquired as a byproduct of interested activity because it is only then that can become a vital part of the students mind and personality and influence his behavior”. But the “Art of

living” is much more comprehensive concept than the acquisition of knowledge. How ever intelligently planned. It includes training in the habit and graces of social life and the capacity for co-operative group works. It calls for patience, good temper, sincerity, fellow-felling and discipline. These objectives can only be cultivated in the context of the social life and the many Co-Curricular activities must find a recognized places in any schools”.

Indian Education commission (1964-66) stressed the important of Co-Curricular activities in these words, “ we conceive of the school curriculum as the totally of the learning experience that the school provides for the pupil through all the main fold activities, In the school or outside that are carried on under its supervision from this point of view, the distinction between CO-curricular and Extracurricular work classes to exist and a school camp games are curricular or rather Co-Curricular activities.”

Role of Co-Curricular Activities

Changes in the philosophical sociological and psychological ideas have now given a new direction to the school curriculum. Philosophical and sociological ideas have brought about a change in the concept of education. The major need of the hour is the ‘education for democracy’ and hence education must aim at producing those individuals who can intelligently and amiably participate in the various activities of life. Traditional curriculum has failed to meet the demands of changing concept of education. The Co-Curricular programme is a convenient tool by which an inadequate curriculum may be modified.

A consideration of psychological factors urges upon the necessity of giving more and more attention to understand the individual difference between the children and of providing proper outlets for the flow of energies to the children. These activities are very helpful in this regard.

Thus, it can be said that Co-Curricular activities provide essential pathway to the students for development their intellectual, physical more as well as vocational attitudes and provides valuable strength to the nation.

“Learning by doing, learning by experience, learning and learning without tears are the main characteristics features of New Education”.

Advantages of Co-Curricular Activities

The education advantages of Co-Curricular are many as well as varied. Some of the Important advantage derived from these are detailed here. The teaching of history, Composition, Geography etc. can be greatly supplemented to elect the student’s council would give them a picture of central and state elections. Excursion to historical, Geographical and Industrial places enrich the experience of the students waiting for the school magazine

supplements the teaching of languages, similarly there are practice activities which offer opportunities to supplement class room work.

It is common knowledge that aesthetic sensibility cannot be taught but it is accepted and developed through real programmes. Participation in dance, dramas fancy dress activities, flower shows etc. by the students provide them opportunities to their aesthetic value.

Games, NCC Physical drill etc. contribute to the physical development of the individual.

Activities like visits, celebration of community festivals, dance, drama etc. enable the students to get knowledge of cultural heritage and develop cultural values.

By participating in Co-Curricular programmes' students learn to cooperate with each other, develop leadership qualities, etc. Co-Curricular activities like social services, etc. develop the attitude of dignity of labor.

Students get opportunities of social contact; they also get opportunities of doing social services. This teaches them the lesson of moral values; they acquire the virtues of honesty, sympathy and good etiquettes.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be said that Co-Curricular activities provide an essential pathway to the students for developing their intellectual, physical, mental, moral as well as vocational attitudes and provide valuable strength to the nation.

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